
Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To Improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following style and guidelines.

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or with small-scale studies in grams per pot (g pot) or grams per row (g row)
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N/ha; not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out in full the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were . . . or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in . . .
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing 10 or some numbers higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the *IRRN* should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common – not trade – names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in *IRRN* contributions.
- Pest surveys should have quantified data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Agronomic characteristics

Inheritance of plant height in a cross of two cold-tolerant rice varieties

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Height of the rice plant is an important morphological character that is thought to be monogenically or polygenically controlled. Understanding height inheritance is important to the development of appropriate plant types.

A cross between indica rice VLK39 and japonica rice VL8 has extremely high variability for plant height. Both strains have been released for hill areas and are cold tolerant. VLK39 is a selection from the cross China 1039/IR580. VL8 is a selection from Kaohsiung 22. The F_1 was taller than either parent, thus exhibiting overdominance or complementary effect of plant height genes.

Frequency distribution of plant height of F_2 population of the cross between VLK39 (P_1) and VL8 (P_2).

Height of the transplanted F_2 of 543 plants ranged from 60 to 165 cm. Because parent height range was continuous, the segregation could not be classified as monogenic. The frequency distribution was not normal so the segregation was not polygenic (see figure).

The frequency distribution was negatively skewed and highly leptokurtic with a very steep peak, indicating the possibility of digenic segregation in the expected genotypic frequencies of 1:2 : 2:4:4 : 2:1. However, because environmental fluctuations made it impossible to differentiate between so many phenotypic classes, an attempt was made to fit plant heights into the digenic ratio of 9:7. The F_2 population was grouped into two classes using 105 cm, the height of the taller parent, as the bifurcation point. This split the population into 323:220 plants, which corresponds with

the 9:7 ratio with a X^2 value of 2.29, nonsignificant at 1% level. Results confirmed the hypothesis that the height variability of the cross results from digenic segregation with complementary gene effects because each parent has one

of the dominant genes. Segregates had from early to medium growth duration and there was no obvious association between plant height and growth duration.

The shortest plants in the segregating

population were much shorter than the shortest parent and are double recessives, making them of great significance as representatives of a new source of dwarfing obtained by combining two recessive genes. □

Ratoon performance of some short-duration rice cultures

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Twenty rice varieties constituting the ninth International Rice Yield Nursery

(early) were grown in three replications at Pattambi during the 1981 kharif. Seedlings were transplanted at 15 cm × 10 cm spacing and received 70-35-35 kg NPK/ha. The main crop was harvested to leave 15-cm-tall stubble and entries were assessed for ratoon performance. The ratoon crop was not fertilized or sprayed.

It was not irrigated but 625 mm of rain fell over 38 rainy days.

Varietal differences in the ratoon yields were significant. Five IRRI lines —IR9209-48-3-2, IR9761-19-1, IR13427-40-2-3-3, IR13429-109-2-2-1, and IR13429-287-3 – were promising (see table). □

Main crop and ratoon performance of some rice varieties at Pattambi, India.

Variety	Duration (days)		Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Main crop	Ratoon crop	Main crop	Ratoon crop
BAU2-3-43	108	56	3.2	0.1
BKN7033-13-1-1-3-2	108	56	3.8	0.2
BPT1235	110	54	4.4	0.1
BR109-74-2-2-2	119	45	3.7	0.2
BR161-2B-58	117	47	3.5	0.2
Chianung Sen yu 13	113	51	3.6	0.4
IR9209-48-3-2	104	60	4.9	0.3
IR9761-19-1	103	61	4.9	0.3
IR9828-91-2-3	108	56	4.0	0.1
IR13427-40-2-3-3	113	51	4.6	0.5
IR13427-60-1-3-2-2	103	61	4.8	0.2
IR13429-109-2-2-1	108	56	4.6	0.4
IR13429-196-1	108	56	4.9	0.2
IR13429-287-3	113	51	4.8	0.3
MRC603-303	109	55	3.7	0.2
MTU34 19	116	48	3.6	0.0
Taichung Sen Yu 285	113	51	3.6	0.4
TNAU1756	103	61	3.8	0.1
IR36	108	56	4.2	0.2
KAU23332-2	113	51	4.5	0.1
CD ($P=0.05$)	—	—	0.55	0.21

Audiovisual cropping systems research modules

IRRI is producing a planned 45-module series of audiovisual lessons in cropping systems research, to include modules on: site selection and description, improved cropping systems design, preproduction testing, and component technology development and evaluation. Two modules, The morphology of maize and An introduction to cropping systems, are available for purchase. For further information write: IRRI, Communication and Publication Dept., Division R, P.O. Box 933, Manila, Philippines

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Promising TKM6 rice mutants

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TKM6 (GEB24/Co 18 hybrid derivative) mutants were isolated after gamma irradiation and treatment with chemical mutagens ethyl methane sulfonate (EMS)

and di-ethyl sulfate (DES) either singly or in combination. Several dwarf mutants were isolated from the different treatments in M2 generation. Among them, three dwarf macromutants were identified as promising and grown through M3 and M4 (see table).

The dwarf mutant obtained with a 30 kR gamma ray dose was early maturing and had reduced leaf area, grain size,

and total dry matter production, but higher per day production, chlorophyll content, number of grains per panicle, and harvest index. The mutant obtained by combining treatments of 35 kR gamma rays + 30 mM EMS had greater leaf area, chlorophyll content, and per day productivity than the control. The third mutant, obtained with a 35 kR gamma ray dose, yielded higher than the